

School Administrators' Personality Traits: Its Relationship to Teachers' Performance

Harly Israel G. Bandojo¹, Felicisimo V. Wenceslao, Jr.², Helen A. Gasapo³

¹Division of Iloilo, Department of Education, Estancia, Iloilo, Philippines

²School of Education, Northern Iloilo Polytechnic State College, Estancia, Iloilo

³School of Education, Northern Iloilo Polytechnic State College, Estancia, Iloilo

ABSTRACT: This descriptive study ascertained the perceived personality traits of school administrators' and its relationship to teachers' performance in public elementary schools in the district of Estancia, Iloilo. The respondents of the study were the ninety (90) purposively selected public elementary teachers from the district of Estancia, Iloilo during the school year 2017-2018. A researcher-made questionnaire which was validated and reliability tested was used. The results revealed that the school administrators had strong personality traits as perceived by the respondents, when taken as a whole and when classified as to age (above 30 years old), sex, civil status, length of service and highest educational attainment. However, those who were 30 years old and below perceived that school administrators have very strong personality traits. In terms of school administrators' physical traits, teachers perceived school administrators to have very strong physical traits except for those who aged above 30 years old and master's degree holders who perceived school administrators to have strong physical traits. In terms of school administrators' social traits, teachers perceived school administrators to have strong social traits except for those who aged 30 years old and below who perceived school administrators to have very strong social traits. In terms of emotional traits and moral traits, teachers perceived school administrators in both aspects to have strong emotional traits and strong moral traits in all categories. The teachers in the district of Estancia, Iloilo had a very satisfactory performance when taken as a whole and when classified as to age, sex, civil status, length of service and highest educational attainment. Results further revealed no significant differences in teachers' performance in the district of Estancia, Iloilo. Moreover, no significant relationship between the school administrators' personal traits and teachers' performance was found.

KEYWORDS: school administrators, personality traits, teachers' performance

I. INTRODUCTION

A teacher, as a person and as a professional, is depicted as a wellspring of knowledge and skill and a model of values, thus deserving to be called a professional. Competent, compassionate, and caring, his attributes are reciprocated with love, respect and emulation. Such is a rewarding life of a teacher (Salandanan, 2012). Teachers develop performance style characteristics to their ways of relating to the world, perceptually as well as cognitively. A person is likely to act in a way that maximizes the use of his abilities. Similarly, teachers' positive attitude towards teaching and higher aspiration level determines his positive perception of the environment. It is universally recognized that teachers' instructional performance plays a key role in students; learning and academic achievement (Bantillo, 2016).

Personality trait affects the amount of work a person does. A teacher can offer his best if his feelings about his work, his association in the job and the social system in which he is employed is secure (Robinson, 2007).

While on the job, the performance of each teacher is influenced, stimulated, extended, hindered, supported, blocked, or ignored by others with whom he/she is interacting (Pandosen, 2006). He further revealed that the prestige of teachers is seen to be declining due to work overload, substandard school facilities, low salaries and pressures from unscrupulous superiors to debase the profession and adversely affect teachers' academic performance and attitudes. As most school administrators in the public elementary schools have shown expertise on administrative functions it would be interesting to find out school administrators' perceived personality traits and its relationship to the performance of teachers.

In the study of Adegbesan (2013) revealed that school principals administrative styles and approach to teachers wherein appropriate and harsh. Another factor which affects teachers' performance is still adequate incentives and lack of adequately motivation and encouragement. Therefore, school administrators, personality traits have a significant relationship to teacher's performance.

School Administrators' Personality Traits: Its Relationship to Teachers' Performance

Wilson, Floden, and Ferrini-Mundy (2001) in their review of the research on teacher preparation conducted for the U.S Department of Education revealed empirical studies conform to variety of accepted methodological approaches and a use a range of measures of teacher effectiveness are used to ascertain what existing evidence says about the relationship between teacher attributes and their performance. In addition, this approach paid close attention to a number of contextual factors as a way of drawing conclusions across studies. Clearly, the context of teaching was important and may affect the impact of the teacher attributes considered in this analysis. In fact, when existing studies were considered as a whole, findings tend to be existent across studies; context variable may help to explain the apparent inconsistency of the existing research.

Since time immemorial, people believe that age matters. As man becomes older, his physical, psychological and intellectual abilities tend to decline. However, the opposite is true when it comes to his experience. Age affects the performance of an individual as considered it as a length of time of life. Moreover, people aged differently because they have different heredity endowments, different socio-economical and educational backgrounds and different patterns of living. Normally, as person grows in age, his physical health deteriorates. As Shah and Udgaonkar (2018) argued, experience increased as the age advanced. Age is traditionally an asset to an individual, a most accessible variable, which is added to a person's resume. Catolos and Catolos (2017) concluded that age is significant on the teaching performance. It is a biological fact that man categories into masculine and feminine. Gender roles are learned patterns of behaviour expected in any society. Because the social status of male is superior to that of female, gender roles both reflect and reinforce a pattern of man dominance and female domination. The work experienced by men is called "technical" but management and male workers say that women do require "little technical skills". The general cross-sectional tendency has been for men to have more domineering and those women to be more passive and nurturing than men.

is added to a person's resume.

Bhuman (2004) in her study "Female leadership holds special relevance for the 21st century" reported that for companies to survive in the next millennium, the boss must give way to management styles that is more empowering supportive and nurturing, sharing relationship and traits that are ascribed by pre-dominantly male respondents more to women than men.

This is state of being married and unmarried. Marriage can make or unmake an executive, more especially a Filipino executive. A happily married executive is more stable as a leader than a separated or unhappily married executive. There is accumulating body of data that there are some women who became successful in male dominated profession tend to be married and have children (Umali, 2010 citing Napiza, 2003). Although conventional wisdom that marriage and children are impediments to women's career, the seemingly paradox is explained. First, their marital and motherhood statues showed a normal women's life. This made them more acceptable working partner to men who regarded women as interested in the social opportunities that worked offered.

Generally, teachers who are new in the service follow the personal qualities being practiced by their school administrator. On the contrary, teachers who belong to age bracket above 30 years old have already adjusted themselves and have coping mechanisms in dealing with their school administrators' personality traits. De Villa (2007, as cited by Umali, 2010) found out in his study that most of the teacher-in-charge belongs to the old age; it is perceived that they are well experienced in creating plans for the school and they have seen steps in achieving the school's goals.

Abarro, (2018) found out that variables such as civil status, highest educational attainment, and local seminars attended and scholastic performance are factors affecting the performance of teachers, while, sex, age, types of family, religion, type of high school attended, LET performance, length of service, annual salary, number of preparations in teaching, international/national/regional seminars attended do not affect the performance of teachers. Macalino (2015) found out in his study that dedicated, hardworking and found teaching as an enjoyable profession and executes their teaching task honestly leads to a very satisfactory teaching performance.

Rizzo (2004) conducted a study about teacher's and supervisor's perceptions of current and ideal supervision and evaluation practices. The study revealed a congruence on the ideal scale between teachers and supervisors with both groups, indicating that effective supervision consists of a collaborative approach involving a variety of models as more frequent visitations and as more trusting and open relationship between the supervisor and the teacher. There was also a significant difference between school types in the areas of differentiated supervision models, clearly articulated performance standards, and teacher being part of the progress of developing the methods by which they are supervised.

With regards to the relationship of school administrators and teaching performance, Gede and Lawanson (2011) in their study revealed that there is a significant relationship between experienced and teaching performance of employees. They found out this relationship exists probably due to the fact that the more experienced employees' gathers as a result of long years of service, the higher the performance of the employee because he/she has to put into practice all the experiences he/she has acquired over the years. This is in support to the findings of Rugai and Agih (2008) who found a high relationship between teacher experience and their teaching performance. They explained that the longer a teacher works in a school, the greater probability that his/her productivity will be higher.

School Administrators' Personality Traits: Its Relationship to Teachers' Performance

According to Rice (2013), a teacher experience is one of the key factors in personal policies that affect employees'. She further opines that experience promotes effectiveness of the teacher. In her study, she observes that teachers showed greatest productivity gains during their first few years of teaching after which their performance tends to diminish.

To this effect, we wanted to find out the school administrators' personality traits and its relationship to teachers' performance in public elementary schools in the Schools District of Estancia, Iloilo. The administrators' personality traits as to physical, social, emotional and moral were perceived by the teachers being classified as to age, sex, civil status, length of service, and highest educational attainment.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study used descriptive research design to determine the perceived school administrators' personality traits and its relationship to teachers' performance. Descriptive research design is a study designed to depict the participants in an accurate way. It is concerned with conditions in relationships that exist, opinions that are held, processes that are going on, effects that are violent, or trends that are developing. It is primarily concerned with the present, although it often considers past events and influences as they are related to current conditions. Likewise, descriptive research deals with relationship between variables, the testing hypothesis and the development of generalization, principles or theories that have universal validity. It is concerned with functional relationships (Shields & Rangarajan, 2013).

B. Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the ninety (90) permanent teachers from the eleven (11) public elementary schools in the district of Estancia, Iloilo. The teacher respondents were selected purposively. The obtained sample size was determined using G*Power software. The percentage of the population of teachers of different schools out of the total population were identified then multiply to the obtained sample size.

Out of the ninety (90) respondents, 10 (10%) were from Andres S. Ravena Elementary School, 7 (7.8%) were from Bayas Elementary School, 7 (7.8%) were from Botongon Elementary School, 4 (4.44%) were from Cano-an Elementary School, 32 (36.61%) were from Estancia Central Elementary School, 3 (3.33%) were from Loguingot Elementary School, 5 (5.56%) were from Lumbia Elementary School, 3 (3.33%) were from Malbog Elementary School, 9 (10%) were from Pa-on Elementary School, 3 (3.33%) were from San Roque Elementary School and 7 (7.78%) were from Tanza Elementary School. Figure 1 shows the distribution of respondents by school.

Figure 1: Distribution of Respondents by School.

The respondents were classified into five variables: age, sex, civil status, length of service, and highest educational attainment. When the respondents were classified as to age, 39 (43.33%) were 30 years old and below and 51(56.67%) were above 30 years old. When classified as to sex, 26(28.89%) were male teachers and 64(71.11%) were female teachers. When classified as to civil status, 42(46.67%) were single teachers and 48(53.33%) were married teachers. In terms of length of service, 69(76.67%) had served 20 years and below while there were 21(23.33%) teachers who served above 20 years. When classified as to educational attainment, 82(91.11%) were bachelor's degree holders while 8(8.89%) were with masters' degree.

School Administrators' Personality Traits: Its Relationship to Teachers' Performance

Figure 2: Distribution of Respondents by Categories.

C. Data Gathering Instruments

This study used a researcher-made-questionnaire to gather the needed data. The questionnaire was subjected to validity and reliability testing. It is composed of two parts, Part I sought personal information of the respondents such as: name, age, sex, civil status, length of service, and highest educational attainment. Part II-A ascertained the school administrators' personality traits as to physical traits, social traits, emotional traits, and moral traits.

The questionnaire was submitted to a panel of four (4) expert jurors for validation. The statements that were found irrelevant were omitted and replaced according to the revisions, suggestions and corrections of the jurors. To ensure its reliability, the questionnaire were tested to thirty (30) permanent teachers of Balasan Central Elementary School, Balasan, Iloilo. Cronbach Alpha was used in determining the reliability of the instrument. The test instrument was found reliable with 0.918 result.

Another instrument used was the Individual Performance Commitment Record Form (IPCRF) of the Department of Education. The respondents' over-all rating performance based on the Appraisal System were utilized.

D. Data Gathering Procedure

Prior to the conduct of the study, permission letter was sent to the Public Schools District Supervisor and to the eleven (11) school administrators, principals, head teachers and teacher-in-charge in the Schools District of Estancia, Iloilo to allow the researchers to administer the study and to gather the IPCRF over-all rating of the 90 permanent teachers. The instrument was personally administered by the researchers among the respondents with the help of the district liaison officer and grade head teachers. The IPCRF were collected from the Office of the District Supervisor signed by the rater, school administrators, principals, head teachers, and teacher-in-charge. Upon retrieval of all accomplished instrument, the data gathered were tallied, computed, analyzed, and interpreted using the IBM SPSS Statistics v.20.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. School Administrators' Personality Traits as Perceived by the Respondents when taken as a Whole and when Classified as to Certain Categories

The respondents evaluated the physical traits of the school administrators in the district of Estancia. When taken as a whole, they were perceived to have very strong physical traits ($M=4.57$, $SD=0.49$). When classified according to age, those who were 30 years old and below ($M=4.69$, $SD=0.35$) have very strong physical traits while those who were above 30 years old have strong physical traits ($M=4.48$, $SD=0.56$). As to sex, both male ($M=4.64$, $SD=0.39$) and female ($M=4.54$, $SD=0.53$) respondents perceived their school administrators to have very strong physical traits. When classified as to civil status, both single ($M=4.58$, $SD=0.57$) and married ($M=4.56$, $SD=0.48$) respondents perceived their school administrators to have very strong physical traits. When they were classified as to length of service, those who were 20 years and below in service ($M=4.56$, $SD=0.50$) and those above 20 years in service ($M=4.61$, $SD=0.48$) both perceived school administrators had very strong physical traits. As to highest educational attainment, those who have bachelors' degree ($M=4.59$, $SD=0.47$) perceived that school administrators had very strong physical traits while respondents with masters' degree holder ($M=4.34$, $SD=0.64$) respondents perceived their school administrators to have strong physical traits.

When the school administrators' personality traits were evaluated in terms of social traits, they were perceived to have strong social traits ($M=4.28$, $SD=0.71$) when taken as a whole. When respondents were classified as to age, those who were 30 years old and below ($M=4.54$, $SD=0.54$) perceived their school administrators to have very strong social traits while those who were above 30 years old perceived school administrators to have strong social traits ($M=4.08$, $SD=0.77$). When classified as to sex, both male

School Administrators' Personality Traits: Its Relationship to Teachers' Performance

(M=4.44, SD=0.61) and female (M=4.22, SD=0.74) respondents perceived their school administrators to have strong social traits. As to civil status, both single (M=4.42, SD=0.66) and married teachers (M=4.16, SD=0.74) perceived school administrators to have strong social traits. When the respondents were classified according to length of service, respondents with 20 years and below in service (M=4.28, SD=0.69) and those with above 20 years in service (M=4.27, SD=0.79) perceived school administrators to have strong social traits. When classified according to highest educational attainment, the respondents who are bachelors' degree holders (M=4.30, SD=0.69) perceived that school administrators had strong social traits while those who were masters' degree holders (M=4.14, SD=0.95) perceived that school administrators had strong social traits.

In terms of emotional traits as perceived by the respondents, the school administrators in the district of Estancia were perceived by the respondents to have strong emotional traits (M=4.15, SD=0.80) when taken as a whole. When classified according to age, either the 30 years old and below (M=4.38, SD=0.66) and those above 30 years old (M=3.98, SD=0.86) respondents perceived their school administrators to have strong emotional traits. When classified as to sex, both male (M=4.47, SD=0.55) and female (M=4.03, SD=0.85) respondents recognized their school administrators to have strong emotional traits. As to civil status, both the single (M=4.35, SD=0.72) and married (M=3.98, SD=0.83) respondents agreed that their school administrators have strong emotional traits. When the respondents were classified according to length of service, the 20 years and below in service (M=4.18, SD=0.77) and those above 20 years in service (M=4.06, SD=0.92) respondents settled in their perception that their school administrators had strong emotional traits. When classified according to highest educational attainment, the bachelors' degree holders (M=4.16, SD=0.77) and those with masters' degree (M=4.05, SD=1.09) perceived that their school administrators have strong emotional traits.

When the respondents evaluated their school administrators' personality traits in terms of moral traits, they perceived them to have strong moral traits (M=4.16, SD=0.85) when taken as a whole. When they were classified according to age, both categories, 30 years old and below (M=4.49, SD=0.59) and above 30 years old (M=3.90, SD=0.93), believed that their school administrators have strong moral traits. When classified as to sex, male (M=4.41, SD=0.59) and female (M=4.05, SD=0.91) respondents saw their school administrators to have strong moral traits. When classified as to civil status, both single (M=4.39, SD=0.74) and married teachers (M=3.95, SD=0.89) perceived school administrators to have strong moral traits. Similarly, those with 20 years and below in service (M=4.21, SD=0.78), those above 20 years in service (M=3.99, SD=1.03), those with bachelors' degree (M=4.18, SD=0.81) and those with masters' degree holder (M=3.95, SD=1.24) perceived their school administrators to have strong moral traits. Table 1 shows the data.

Table 1: School Administrators' Personality Traits as Perceived by the Respondents when taken as an Entire Group and when Classified as to Certain Categories.

Categories	n	Physical Traits			Social Traits			Emotional Traits			Moral Traits			
		Mean	SD	Description	Mean	SD	Description	Mean	SD	Description	Mean	SD	Description	
A. Entire group	90	4.57	0.49	Very Strong	4.28	0.71	Strong	4.15	0.8	Strong	4.16	0.85	Strong	
B. Age	=< 30 years old	39	4.69	0.35	Very strong	4.54	0.54	Very strong	4.38	0.66	Strong	4.49	0.59	Strong
	>30 years old	51	4.48	0.56	Strong	4.08	0.77	Strong	3.98	0.86	Strong	3.9	0.93	Strong
C. Sex	Male	26	4.64	0.39	Very Strong	4.44	0.61	Strong	4.47	0.56	Strong	4.41	0.59	Strong
	Female	64	4.54	0.53	Very Strong	4.22	0.74	Strong	4.03	0.85	Strong	4.05	0.91	Strong
D. Civil Status	Single	42	4.58	0.5	Very Strong	4.42	0.66	Strong	4.35	0.72	Strong	4.39	0.74	Strong
	Married	48	4.56	0.48	Very Strong	4.16	0.74	Strong	3.98	0.83	Strong	3.95	0.89	Strong
E. Length of Service	=< 20 years	69	4.56	0.5	Very Strong	4.28	0.69	Strong	4.18	0.77	Strong	4.21	0.78	Strong
	> 20 years	21	4.61	0.48	Very Strong	4.27	0.79	Strong	4.06	0.92	Strong	3.99	1.03	Strong
F. Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelors' Degree	82	4.59	0.47	Very Strong	4.30	0.69	Strong	4.16	0.77	Strong	4.18	0.81	Strong
	Masters' Degree	8	4.34	0.64	Strong	4.14	0.95	Strong	4.05	1.09	Strong	3.95	1.24	Strong

Note: 4.41-5.00 (*Very Strong*); 3.51-4.50 (*Strong*); 2.51-3.50 (*Moderate*); 1.51-2.50 (*Weak*); 1.00-1.50 (*Very Weak*)

School Administrators' Personality Traits: Its Relationship to Teachers' Performance

B. Public Elementary Schools Teacher's Performance when taken as a Whole and when Classified as to Certain Categories

The performances of the public elementary school teachers were taken from the IPCRF during the SY 2016-2017. The results showed that when taken as a whole, public elementary school teachers in the district of Estancia, had very satisfactory performance ($M=3.82$, $SD=0.15$). When classified according to age, those who are 30 years old and below ($M=3.80$, $SD=0.11$) and those who were above 30 years old ($M=3.84$, $SD=0.17$) had very satisfactory performance. When classified as to sex, male teachers ($M=3.83$, $SD=0.07$) and female teachers ($M=3.82$, $SD=0.17$) had very satisfactory performance. As to civil status, both single ($M=3.81$, $SD=0.15$) and married ($M=3.84$, $SD=0.15$) teachers had very satisfactory performance. When the teachers were classified according to length of service, respondents with 20 years and below in service ($M=3.82$, $SD=0.13$) and those above 20 years in service ($M=3.85$, $SD=0.19$) had also very satisfactory performance. When classified according to highest educational attainment, the respondents with bachelors' degree ($M=3.82$, $SD=0.15$) and those with masters' degree holder had very satisfactory performance. Table 2 shows the data.

Table 2: Public Elementary Schools Teacher's Performance when taken as a Whole and Classified as to Certain Categories

Categories	n	Mean	SD	Description
A. Entire group	90	3.82	0.15	Very Satisfactory
B. Age				
=< 30 years old	39	3.8	0.11	Very Satisfactory
>30 years old	51	3.84	0.17	Very Satisfactory
C. Sex				
Male	26	3.83	0.07	Very Satisfactory
Female	64	3.82	0.17	Very Satisfactory
D. Civil Status				
Single	42	3.81	0.15	Very Satisfactory
Married	48	3.84	0.15	Very Satisfactory
E. Length of Service				
=< 20 years	69	3.82	0.13	Very Satisfactory
> 20 years	21	3.85	0.19	Very Satisfactory
F. Highest Educational Attainment				
Bachelors' Degree	82	3.82	0.13	Very Satisfactory
Masters' Degree	8	3.85	0.19	Very Satisfactory

Note: 4.41-5.00 (*Very Strong*); 3.51-4.50 (*Strong*); 2.51-3.50 (*Moderate*); 1.51-2.50 (*Weak*); 1.00-1.50 (*Very Weak*)

C. Difference in Teacher's Performance when Classified as to Certain Categories

Using the Mann-Whitney U Test revealed that there was no significant differences in teachers' performance in public elementary schools in the district of Estancia when classified as to age ($n=90$; $U=890.50$; $z=-0.871$; $p=0.384$). It implies that the performance of the 30 years old and below ($Md=3.80$, $n=39$) were the same or did not differ with the performance of those above 30 years old ($Md=3.80$, $n=51$).

When classified as to sex, no significant difference was noted ($n=90$; $U=693.50$; $z=-1.268$; $p=0.205$). This means that the performance of male ($Md=3.80$, $n=26$) and female ($Md=3.80$, $n=64$) teachers in public elementary schools in the district of Estancia was not statistically different and considered the same. Also, there was no significant difference on the performance of teachers when classified according to civil status ($n=90$; $U=887.00$; $z=-1.007$; $p=0.314$) as shown in the performances of single ($Md=3.80$, $n=42$) and married ($Md=3.80$, $n=48$) teachers.

When classified according to length of service ($n=90$; $U=625.00$; $z=-0.977$; $p=0.329$), results showed no significant difference in the performance of teachers with 20 years and below ($Md=3.80$, $n=69$) in service and those having served for above 20 years ($Md=3.80$, $n=21$).

Moreover, there was no significant difference noted on the performance of teachers when classified according to highest educational attainment ($n=90$; $U=254.00$; $z=-1.079$; $p=0.280$). Teachers with bachelor's degree ($Md=3.80$, $n=82$) do not differ statistically with the performance of those with master's degree holder ($Md=3.85$, $n=8$).

School Administrators' Personality Traits: Its Relationship to Teachers' Performance

The results conform to the findings of Abarro (2018) which state that variables such as civil status, highest educational attainment, and scholastic performance are factors affecting the performance of teachers, while, sex, age, types of family, religion, type of high school attended, LET performance, length of service, annual salary, number of preparations in teaching, international/national/regional seminars attended do not affect the performance of teachers. The data are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Difference on Teacher's Performance when classified as to Certain Categories

Teachers' Performance	n	Md	U	z	p
A.Age					
= < 30 years old	39	3.8	890.5	-0.871	0.384
> 30 years old	51	3.8			
B.Sex			693.5	-1.268	0.205
Male	26	3.8			
Female	64	3.8			
C.Civil Status			887	-1.007	0.314
Single	42	3.8			
Married	48	3.8			
D.Length of Service			625	-0.977	0.329
= < 20 years	69	3.8			
> 20 years	21	3.8			
E.Highest Educational Attainment			254	-1.079	0.28
Bachelors' Degree	82	3.8			
Masters' Degree	8	3.85			

Note: $p > 0.05$ not significant

D. Relationship between the School Administrators' Personality Traits and Teachers' Performance

Table 4 presents the relationship between the school administrators' personality traits and teachers' performance in the district of Estancia. Statistical analysis revealed that there is no significant relationship between school administrators' personality traits and teachers' performance ($n=90$, $\rho=0.137$, $p=0.199$) since the p-value appeared higher than the set alpha level. This implies that the teachers' performance was not related to the school administrators' personality traits as perceived by the teachers and the personality traits of the school administrators' did not affect the performance of teachers. The results conform to the findings of Maurer (2012) which was dismissed as likely the result of principal's awarding higher scores to teachers with personality traits they found more desirable. Positive traits may not have significantly predicted teachers' performance.

Table 4: Relationship between the School Administrators' Personality Traits and Teachers' Performance

	n	rho	p
Personality Traits vs Teachers' Performance	90	0.137	0.199

Note: $p > 0.05$ not significant

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The personality traits of school administrators in public elementary schools in the district of Estancia, Iloilo as perceived by the teachers was found to be strong when taken as a whole and when classified according to age, sex, civil status, length of service and highest educational attainment and very strong for 30 years old and below. This may be because the school administrators wanted to gain the respect of their teachers that they projected and maintained strong personality traits.

The teachers' performance in public elementary schools in the district of Estancia, Iloilo were very satisfactory when taken as a whole and when classified as to age, sex, civil status, length of service, and the highest educational attainment. Their very satisfactory performance was attributed to prompt submission and updated implementation of what was required of them to be performed inside and outside of the classroom may it be instruction or delegation.

The results revealed no significant differences in the teachers' performance when classified according to age, sex, civil status, length of service, and highest educational attainment. This may mean that regardless of their age, sex, civil status, length of service and highest educational attainment, the teachers' performance in public elementary schools in the district of Estancia, Iloilo did not differ.

School Administrators' Personality Traits: Its Relationship to Teachers' Performance

The perceived school administrators' personality traits and teachers' performance were not statistically related with each other. School administrators' personal traits did not affect teachers' performance and teachers' performance was not influenced by school administrators' personality traits.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were advanced:

1. The school administrators in public elementary schools in the district of Estancia, Iloilo, may consider to demonstrate desirable physical, social, emotional and moral traits at all times to ensure the continuous improvement among teachers' performance.

2. The school administrators may include topics on development of interpersonal relations with others during the in-service training programs for teachers. In this way, teachers may gain pointers in coping with the personality traits of their school administrators to develop a good school administrator-teacher relation.

3. Teachers may work on developing in themselves the right attitudes and correct habits when dealing with their school administrators which may lead to a very strong school administrator-teachers relation and may improve their performance eventually.

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School Administrators' Personality Traits: Its Relationship to Teachers' Performance

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